

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL COOPERATION IN PRODUCTION WITH THE WEST IN SOCIALIST BULGARIA

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Abstract

As a result of the scientific and technical cooperation in production with the West, a technological leap has been achieved in Bulgaria, which strengthens and expands the industrial development that has begun and creates a favorable climate for international cooperation, which breaks the ideological prejudices characteristic of the time. The close contacts established with Western specialists and the implemented contracts for joint production, transfer of technology and know-how significantly expand, on the one hand, the industrial base in Bulgaria, lead to the emergence of completely new production and establish the Bulgarian economy as one of the modern machine-building countries with its own important place in the international division of labor. On the other hand, many Western companies have opened up prospects for sharing technological experience, opportunities for penetrating new market territories and creating long-term fruitful trade and friendly relations with the technical intelligentsia of Bulgarian society.

Keywords: history, economy, technology, cooperation, industry, east, west

The idea of presenting economic cooperation with the West during socialism in Bulgaria aims to show a positive trend in relations in the second half of the 20th century. Here, the political reasons aimed at thawing relations between countries that otherwise belong to two ideologically and economically different military-political blocs are not considered, but rather the positive results that occur as a result of technical cooperation in production between Western companies and Bulgarian business organizations.

The terms "Western", "Eastern", "West" and "East", used in the text, should be understood in the full sense given to them by the rhetoric in the second half of the 20th century.

The aim of this study is to show several cases of cooperation leading to positive changes that are occurring in our country, namely: modernization of the technological park of the industrial base, absorption of new highly effective technologies and productions, which ultimately lead to an increase in labor productivity and make Bulgaria a participant in global development and progress.

The absorption of new technologies and productions directs the Bulgarian economy to the stage of intensive development, takes it out of the autarky characteristic of the first post-war years and expands its opportunities for export to the CMEA member countries and to the market of developing countries, places it in a convenient intermediary position in the international division of labor.

For this purpose, various official documents have been reviewed, including reports and accounts from the Ministry of Mechanical Engineering to the Council of Ministers, which analyze the current situation in Bulgarian and global production, opinions on various directions for development and proposals for the manner and forms of implementing economic cooperation with Western companies. Decisions of the Central Commission on Issues of Production and Technical Cooperation (hereinafter referred to as the Commission), opinions and findings from technical and

memoir literature, as well as opinions from various studies that are relevant to the topic, have also been cited.

For modern times, cooperation between countries, especially in the field of economy and technology, is a natural reality. In the years of global confrontation, when the world is divided into two warring camps, there are a number of factors and circumstances that hinder normal communication between peoples, and the exchange of experience and technological cooperation is severely limited. Regardless of these circumstances, in socialist Bulgaria we find examples of the manifestation of political will for economic cooperation with developed Western countries. What are the reasons for these actions?

The search for cooperation in the field of technology with the West is the result of the realization by the leadership of the Bulgarian state of the unsatisfactory level of development of industry in our country. There is no doubt about the advantage of the West, which has more modern and more effective technical and technological means of production. Moreover, the goal pursued by the Eastern European political elites to catch up and reach the technological level of developed Western countries is well known, and this turns out to be easier if joint cooperation is carried out between them. Lenin also emphasized that a communist society cannot be built if science, technology and art are not taken from capitalism. [1]

For a long time after the end of World War II, the implementation of cooperation between the countries of the East and the West was hindered due to ideological and political reasons, the most vivid and comprehensive expression of which was the Cold War phenomenon, which created conditions for total opposition and competition. Scientific and technical cooperation, in particular, was hindered by the creation, in 1949, on the one hand, of COCOM - a Coordination Committee of representatives of the USA, the European Council, Australia and Japan, which determined lists of strategic goods prohibited for export to the socialist

countries, and on the other hand - by the creation of the CMEA - a Council for Mutual Economic Assistance between the countries of Eastern Europe, which emphasized cooperation only between the socialist countries and aimed at deepening their integration with the USSR.

The cooperation refused by the Western countries was compensated by membership in the CMEA, the organization that offered the countries of Eastern Europe certain opportunities for international cooperation in the economy, trade, science, technology and other public spheres.

Within the framework of the CMEA, Bulgaria received the necessary production experience and access to new scientific and technical achievements for the transition to industrialization, initially from the Soviet Union, and subsequently, with the creation and development of the economic and scientific and technical potential of Bulgaria and the other CMEA member countries, the mutual exchange between them intensified, and a consistent transition from the stage of production to scientific and technical cooperation and integration was observed. [2]

Extremely favorable and decisive for the development of the CMEA member countries is the circumstance that until the end of the 1960s this exchange was mainly free of charge, and then it passed to a commercial basis (*ibid.*, p. 54).

Such a type of cooperation implies a commitment to specialization in specific production areas necessary for inclusion in the international division of labor (within the framework of the CMEA). The issues surrounding the introduction of production specialization among all member states were discussed at the 7th session of the CMEA, where Bulgaria sought to gain positions primarily in mechanical engineering, since development in this area is decisive for the degree of modernization and the construction of an industrial society. Some researchers point out that our partners resisted Bulgaria's desire to specialize in mechanical engineering with the argument that in our country it is at a very low technical level, but the then state leader Todor Zhivkov managed to convince the CMEA member states that Bulgarian mechanical engineering could be competitive if it became a structurally determining sector of our economy, and declared to the Council his intention to achieve this by purchasing Western licenses in order to raise the technological level of Bulgarian industrial production. [3]

The concerns of our economic partners in the CMEA regarding the weak development of mechanical engineering in our country are quite justified given the available data. Almost non-existent before the Second World War, this economic sector developed progressively in the decades after, with its relative share in the total industry increasing from 4.2% in 1948 to 15% in 1960, but compared to the other CMEA member countries, in Bulgaria it was the lowest at that time. [4]

This situation soon changed in a positive direction after the beginning in the mid-1960s of a policy of economic and technological cooperation in mechanical engineering production with developed Western

companies. It should be noted that the idea of using world scientific and technical achievements and experience began to be imposed gradually after 1956, when the notorious April Plenum, famous for its new trends, was held.

Real cooperation in production with Western companies was implemented in the second half of the 1960s in the field of the automotive industry with Italy - assembly of passenger cars in Lovech under license from FIAT. In 1967, production of diesel engines began in Varna under license from the English company Perkins. Joint, cooperative production was established with the West German Kassbohrer (1970) and Varta (1965), etc. These examples are the subject of another study [5]

For the purposes of this report, we will only note that cooperation with them was carried out through the conclusion of license agreements, as a result of which, in return for payment, we received technical documentation, technical assistance and ready-made technology for organizing and implementing both new means of production and new works. We must emphasize that Bulgaria began to develop licensing activities later than other socialist countries, and the purchase of licenses was legally regulated in our country only in 1965 with the approval of the first regulations on the procedure for purchasing them. [2, p. 41]

Cooperation through the acquisition of licenses allows for a very quick overcoming of the technical and technological lag in certain areas and creates opportunities for the development of new sectors in the economy, but the greatest benefit of implementing the license is that it saves time and a lot of money that the licensee, i.e. the person acquiring the license, would have spent on conducting their own scientific and technical research and development. [2, p. 44]

Through this method of cooperation, a number of problems in agriculture, food industry, light industry, pharmaceuticals, mechanical engineering, chemistry and metallurgy have been solved in our country. For the period 1962 - 1985, the licenses purchased by Bulgaria totaled 365, with 74 of them purchased from CMEA member countries, and the remaining 291 were purchased from Western countries. [6]

In the 1970s, the spectrum of Bulgarian interest in economic, industrial and technical cooperation with the West expanded, now encompassing activities in the field of light industry, construction, agriculture, transport, tourism and trade. The Central Commission for Economic and Scientific and Technical Cooperation was established in 1974 by Decision No. 64 of the Politburo of the Central Committee of the Bulgarian Communist Party of 13.02.1974. [7]

Noting that these are processes directly led by the top leadership of the state, it is appropriate to note that Bulgaria is the active country in seeking opportunities for cooperation with developed Western countries.

Among the main goals set by the Commission is the desire to: modernize the existing ones in our country and build new capacities and production facilities based on modern scientific and technical achievements; improve the organization of production and increase

labor productivity; more fully satisfy the needs of the country and expand export opportunities; carry out joint constructive and technological developments, including complete projects and joint ventures in third countries. [ibid.]

There is a sober idea of the state of the means of production in our country and the quality of the production, which is not ideologically hidden behind false illusions with which to manipulate the public. A similar assessment is also attested to in the periodic reports prepared by the Minister of Mechanical Engineering on the state and development of the technological base in our country. Usually it is the main motive for requesting the allocation of additional funds for modernization and reconstruction.

At the very first meeting of the Commission in the spring of 1974, an "Example List of Major Projects for Long-Term Production, Technical and Trade Cooperation with Companies from Western Countries" was adopted. The document is marked "personally strictly confidential". [7, p.24]

Projects of future cooperation with Western companies in the field of mechanical engineering, chemical industry, metallurgy, mining industry, agriculture and food industry, light industry and infrastructure are described.

The first proposal on the list is for cooperation with Western companies in organizing the construction of large-tonnage ships.

The production of large-tonnage ships with a displacement of over 70,000 tons is a goal that Bulgarian mechanical engineering has been persistently pursuing since the late 1940s, but this goal was actually realized only in 1975, with the launching of the 100,000-ton ship "Khan Asparuh". Although not directly responsible for this result, the technical assistance agreement signed in 1971 with "Hitachi Zosen" played a significant role, and on this basis successful cooperation with the largest shipbuilder in Japan was realized. [8]

The cooperation includes training of personnel, consultations on the modernization of the shipyard in Varna, the introduction of progressive technologies and equipment for mechanization and automation of production processes, as well as the submission of a project for a 70,000-ton tanker. [9]

In a report by the Minister of Mechanical Engineering Mariy Ivanov to the Chairman of the Council of Ministers Todor Zhivkov, on the development of shipbuilding in our country until 1975, it is emphasized that for increasing the efficiency of shipbuilding, the acquisition of the production of main ship engines under a license from a world-famous company or, in extreme cases, the purchase of a sublicense from the USSR for the production of engines, brand "Burmester and Wein". [10]

This option was not implemented, but in 1974, the reconstruction of the Mayak machine-building plant in Dobrich was started, where it was planned to start producing diesel engines under the license of the Swiss company Sulzer [9]

And this attempt was unsuccessful. In his memories of that moment, G. Georgiev, executive

director of the Shipbuilding Association, shares that at the suggestion of the member of the Polit Bureau Ognyan Doinov, the construction of a plant for ship diesel engines under the license of Sulzer was stopped in order to study the possibility of this happening under the license of Pilstik. [11]

Regardless of this, a ready-made diesel engine "Sulzer" with a capacity of 23,500 hp was installed on the 100,000-ton Bulgarian tanker "Khan Asparuh", in connection with which the Swiss company shot a special film [11, p. 119]

At a meeting of the Central Commission on issues of production and technical cooperation with non-socialist countries on June 3, 1974, a proposal by Ivan Vrachev, chairman of the Committee for Recreation and Tourism, for trade cooperation with the Swedish construction concern ABV for the construction of a tourist base in our country was also considered. [12]

The report found increased interest among Scandinavians in the mineral resources in our country and based on the discussions held, a proposal was considered for the construction of a year-round hotel with a balneological complex in the Druzhba resort (today St. St. Constantine and Elena). The Swedish side is obliged through its Union of Cooperatives to ensure at least 40% average annual occupancy of the hotel with tourists. According to a Bulgarian architectural project, Swedish civil engineers and specialists carried out the construction and on April 22, 1978, the luxurious complex of the Grand Hotel Varna was officially opened, the work of architect Georgi Ganey and the construction team of the Swedish company ABV. The object is the first implementation of a Bulgarian project by a foreign construction company during the period under review. [13]

The cooperation in the field of construction for the needs of tourism was continued with two French companies. In the summer of 1975, a report was presented to the Commission by the Chairman of the Committee on Recreation and Tourism, Ivan Vrachev, who proposed cooperation with the French companies Sodeteg and Novotel, which would involve the design, financing and joint operation of a tourist base in our country. [14]

Contracts were signed with the two French companies, as a result of which a hotel of the "three-star" category according to French standards was built in Sofia at a cost of 131 million francs, and a luxury hotel in Plovdiv at a cost of 91 million francs. The construction was completed in less than three years, with the Bulgarian side paying with a state export credit from France, and the ownership of the two hotels was purchased after 6 years of joint Bulgarian-French exploitation.

Western companies are showing interest in cooperation in the field of oil and gas exploration and production on the territory of Bulgaria. The Minister of Mineral Resources Stamen Stamenov reported to Zhivkov about talks held with representatives of the American Exxon, the English British Petroleum and Burma Petroleum and the Italian ENTE. [15]

The parties agree on technical cooperation and cooperation on mutually beneficial terms, but due to

poor results in the discovery of oil and gas deposits, the relations do not go beyond good intentions.

In the field of agriculture, great interest is observed on the part of Western companies in cooperation with Bulgarian tobacco producers. During the period under review - the second half of the 20th century. Tobacco production is one of the most well-developed industries in Bulgaria. A report by the Minister of Agriculture and Food Industry Gancho Krastev states that in 1970 120,000 tons of tobacco were produced in our country, and in 1972 - 159,000 tons, tobacco and cigarettes form 27% of the total export of agricultural goods and 13% of the country's total export. [16]

The report of the Minister of Agriculture also notes significant problems in the industry: high labor costs in the production of oriental tobaccos, lack of efficient industrial technology and the presence of outdated equipment. The problems lead to low labor productivity and unsatisfactory quality.

To solve the problems in Bulgarian tobacco and cigarette production, the experience of 14 Western companies, leading in the tobacco industry, was sought. Bulgaria is oriented towards tobacco production in the USA, where industrial processing is highly mechanized and efficient production technologies are applied. [ibid.]

In 1974, an agreement was signed with the American company Universal leaf tobacco for the sowing of 6 varieties of "Virginia" on an area of 750 decares and 3 varieties of "Burley" on 30 decares in the agricultural holdings of the town of Benkovski and the town of Byala Slatina. [ibid.]

The American company supplies the seeds, chemicals, preparations and instructions for production. On its recommendation, another 4,000 plants were delivered from Italy. Parallel experiments were set up with seeds supplied by the Dibrell brothers company. It was agreed with other companies from the USA and Canada to experiment with the latest models for mechanization of the processes in the production of large-leaf tobacco.

The Minister testified in his report to the Commission that 5 complex lines covering different sides of the production and one American combine for mechanized picking are already in operation in our country. He also expects a plant for processing large-leaf tobacco using American technology to be built in our country. Efforts are being made to provide machines from France as well. [ibid.]

Regarding cooperation in cigarette production, meetings and talks were held with the world's largest companies - Philip Morris, Reynolds and Lorillard, USA; British - American Tobacco, GFR and British - American tobacco, UK, and after contracting, under license, cigarettes of the most common brands in the world began to be produced in our country: Winston, Marlboro and HB, in which there is a significant content of Bulgarian tobacco. Separately, cooperative production was launched with the mentioned large Western manufacturers and the brands Zodiac, RB, Champion and Astra appeared on the market, where the content of Bulgarian tobacco is 2/3 of the total quantity.

Work is underway to introduce tobacco blowing technology in our country, which brings some savings in materials. The purchase of a tobacco foil production plant is being discussed. With the companies AMF and Sokotab, "Bulgarian Tobaccos" is planning a joint experiment to test an installation designed to automate tobacco sorting in one of the workshops of the Plovdiv combine.

In parallel with the implementation of cooperation with Western companies, the processes of integration with socialist countries are also strengthening, and Bulgarian positions on the eastern market are being strengthened. According to the report, over 85% of cigarettes and 30% of tobacco imported by the CMEA member states come from Bulgaria. Bulgarian business leaders also see opportunities for exporting our production to non-socialist countries. [ibid.]

The agreement with the Japanese company Fujitsu for industrial cooperation in the production of MOS integrated circuits is extremely successful in terms of the scale of its implementation. [17]

35 million foreign currency leva are provided for the purchase of new technologies, equipment and training of specialists. The agreement obliges the Bulgarian side to consider the Japanese company as a preferred supplier of electronic computing centers without interrupting negotiations with the companies Takeda, Riken, NEC, Hitachi and TDK with a view to signing contracts for cooperation and technical assistance for the provision of electronic test systems, electronic digital multimeters, telephone and radio relay systems with pulse-code modulation, video recording and video playback equipment, etc. (ibid.)

Cooperation with Fujitsu has a history in Bulgaria. As early as 1965, the State Committee for Scientific and Technical Progress was preparing a decision of the Council of Ministers for the development of computing and organizational equipment. Then, cooperation was sought with leading companies such as IBM, ICL, Siemens, etc., with Fujitsu being the first to respond to the Bulgarian invitation. The 5 Facom 230/30 electronic computers purchased from them were implemented in the production of the Computer Plant in Sofia under the name ZIT 151 and by 1970, 20 machines were manufactured there under license [18]

The cooperation with Fujitsu in the field of the electronic industry deepened in the early 1980s in the production of industrial robots using the technology of Fujitsu's subsidiary company Fanuc - a license was purchased for the acquisition of technology for the production of 12 types of industrial robots, implemented in the NPKR "Beroe", Stara Zagora [19]

The development of technology for the production of industrial robots began in 1978 with the approval of the National Coordination Program "Robotics", and for this purpose licenses were purchased from the American company AMR "Verzatan" [6, p. 158]

In 1982, Bulgarian design organization "Mashproekt" developed a project for software support of the entire production system together with Fanuc, which, according to the report of Minister Toncho Chakarov, was the development of experience and a

basis for further design and implementation of flexible automated production systems - GAPS. [19]

In the same year, the National Program GAPS was adopted, for the purposes of which a number of licenses were purchased from Western companies for the modernization of Bulgarian mechanical engineering, among which were Fanuc, Yamazaki, Gildemeister, etc.

Investments in the computerization and automation of production processes lead to positive results, which are reflected in statistics. In 1983, the value of electronic and computing equipment exported to the socialist camp from Bulgaria amounted to 930 million foreign currency levs. [20]

The successful cooperation with Western companies leads to a whole complex of positive results: modernization of the production base and expansion of the machine-building nomenclature; increasing the technological level of Bulgarian production; increasing labor productivity. Bulgarian production becomes competitive on the international market and attractive enough for the opportunities of developing countries, where Bulgaria begins to export machinery, equipment and complete objects in exchange for the import of basic raw materials to meet domestic economic needs. Proof of this is the developed Complex Program for Supplying the Country with Raw Materials from Developing Countries for the Time Range 1976 – 1990. [21]

The main goal of the program is the maximum use of the opportunities for satisfying the needs of Bulgaria with raw materials and materials from developing countries in exchange for participation in the delivery of complete facilities, machinery and equipment, geological exploration, design, construction and installation activities, technical assistance, etc.

According to St. Stamenov, Minister of Mineral Resources, the high rates at which the Bulgarian economy is developing allow it to take an active part in building the economies of developing countries. [22]

Appendix No. 53 to the Complex Program reveals the value of the complete objects, machines and equipment, construction, design, geological and exploration activities planned for export, which amounts to nearly 3 billion foreign currency leva, with 10 state economic organizations and foreign trade enterprises being engaged in their implementation. [23]

To service this export, the Bulgarian organization "Technoexport", established by Decision No. 18 of the Council of Ministers of 23.11.1977, is directly involved in the research, design, export and import of complete objects, technologies, licenses and other activities, including the sending of our specialists abroad to provide scientific and technical assistance. By 1980, "Technoexport" had concluded contracts for the construction of complete objects, separate lines and nodes in the developing countries of Algeria, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Libya, Iraq, Pakistan and other countries in Asia and Latin America, where it sends specialists for construction, installation and technical assistance. [24]

Having once mastered progressive technology from Western companies, Bulgaria managed to occupy for some time the advantageous position of an

intermediary, both for the countries of Eastern Europe and for the developing countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America. This situation brings it closer to the practice of highly developed countries, which owe their advantage in the international division of labor to the technologies they possess and are constantly developing.

In 1982, the export of complete objects to socialist and non-socialist countries was worth a total of 154.3 million foreign currency levs, of which 2/3 were revenues from socialist countries, and 50% of all exports to non-socialist countries were directed to Iraq, and 23.7% to Libya. [25]

Through the implementation of scientific and technical cooperation and cooperation with leading Western companies, as a result of which the production base is equipped with modern equipment, labor productivity and product quality are increased and opportunities for higher competitiveness on the international market are created, Bulgaria manages to rank among the countries with a developed economy. The achieved technological development gives it the opportunity to take part in building the economies of developing countries, which it supports with the export of complete objects, machinery and equipment, with the provision of specialists involved in geological surveys, construction and design activities. The successful implementation of a policy expressed in the establishment of specific economic relations with the West and the East during the period under review places Bulgaria in the advantageous position of an intermediary, which creates an image of a developed country with a modern industrial base, where high-tech production is developed, the result of the work of a technically intelligent society.

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